

Additional file 1 The list of siRNAs used in the study

Gene	NCBI GeneID	Protein, aliases	Viruses	siRNA
		Negative control siRNA		AllStars 0001027280
PVR	5817	CD155, PVR	Polio 1,2,3	Hs_PVR_4 S100089110 Hs_PVR_5 S103070809
ICAM1	3383	ICAM-1, Intracellular adhesion molecule-1, CD54	CV-A13, -18, -21 Major group rhinoviruses	Hs_ICAM1_6 S103093923 Hs_ICAM1_7 S103110576
CXADR	1525	CAR, Coxsackievirus-adenovirus receptor	CV-B1, CV-B2, CV-B3, CV-B4, CV-B5, CV-B6	Hs_CXADR_9 S103023447 Hs_CXADR_11 S103106495
HAVCR1	26762	HAVcr-1; HAV cellular receptor	HAV	Hs_HAVCR1_8 S103093223 Hs_HAVCR1_9 S103100713
CD55	1604	DAF, decay accelerating factor, CD55	E-3, -6, -7, -11, -12, -13, -20, -21, -24, -29, -30 EV-70 CV-B1, CV-B3	Hs_CD55_2 S103075660 Hs_DAF_3 S100012103
ITGB1	3688	Integrin β 1	E-1 FMDV HPeV-1	Hs_ITGB1_5 S100300573 (92%) Hs_ITGB1_9 S102662590 (92%)
ITGB3	3690	Integrin β 3	CV-A9, FMDV, HPeV-1	Hs_ITGB3_1 S100004585 Hs_ITGB3_5 S102623159
ITGB6	3694	Integrin β 6	CV-A9, FMDV	Hs_ITGB6_1 S100017801 Hs_ITGB6_5 S103053029

ITGB8	3696	Integrin β 8	FMDV	Hs_ITGB8_5 SI03030174 Hs_ITGB8_6 SI03066623
ITGA2	3673	Integrin α 2	E-1	Hs_ITGA2_5 SI02664081 (86%) Hs_ITGA2_6 SI02664088 (87%)
ITGA5	3678	Integrin α 5	FMDV	Hs_ITGA5_5 SI02654841 (86%) Hs_ITGA5_7 SI03071572
LDLR	3949	LDL-R, Low-density lipoprotein receptor	Minor group rhinoviruses	Hs_LDLR_3 SI00011179 Hs_LDLR_4 SI00011186
NANS	54187	N-acetylneuraminic acid synthase (sialic acid synthase), SAS	HRV-87 (sialic acid)	Hs_NANS_2 SI00654850 Hs_NANS_5 SI04146345
EXT1	2131	exostosin (multiple) 1; (an ER-resident type II transmembrane glycosyltransferase involved in the chain elongation step of heparan sulfate biosynthesis)	FMDV	Hs_EXT1_1 SI00002562 Hs_EXT1_4 SI00002583
B2M	567	Beta-2-microglobulin	CV-A9, E-1	Hs_B2M_3 SI00059038 Hs_B2M_4 SI00059045